

Ameloblastoma: Pathogenesis, Clinical and Radiological Features, Classification, and Management

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Background: Ameloblastoma are benign epithelial odontogenic tumors affecting the jaws. **Objective:** The main objective of this article is to review the pathogenesis, clinical and radiological features, classification, and management of ameloblastoma. **Methods:** A literature review mainly of the Pubmed database was done using the keywords: “ameloblastoma pathogenesis”; “ameloblastoma classification”; “ameloblastoma history”; “clinical and radiological features of ameloblastoma”; and “management of ameloblastoma”. **Results:** In 2017, ameloblastomas were classified by W.H.O into three categories: a) unicystic, b) conventional, and c) extraosseous/peripheral. Clinically, they are slow-growing, localized, aggressive neoplasms. Radiologically, they mainly present as extensive, radiolucent, multilocular images, with a typical “soap bubble-like” appearance with a thinner, expanded, and eroded cortical plate. The linked non-erupted tooth is displaced and the roots of the adjacent teeth undergo clear resorption. **Conclusion:** Because of their late signs and symptoms, ameloblastomas are usually identified at an advanced stage. Their management typically includes a large resection with safety margins and immediate reconstruction when possible. Regular long-term postoperative follow-ups are mandatory for optimum treatment outcome and recurrence prevention.

Keywords: Ameloblastoma; odontogenic tumor; conventional; unicystic; extraosseous.

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1. BACKGROUND

Ameloblastoma is a rare benign epithelial odontogenic tumor affecting the jaws (1). It accounts for about 1% of all jaws tumors and about 9-11% of all odontogenic ones. It is characterized by its slow-growing local aggressive behavior and a high recurrence rate.

Ameloblastoma is more frequent in the 3rd to 4th decades of life, with a female/male ratio of 1:1 (2). It commonly occurs in the mandible (80% of the cases), especially in the angle and the ramus, and less often in the maxilla (2, 3). Untreated, it infiltrates through the cortical bone and extends to the adjacent tissues (4).

Maxillary ameloblastomas, especially located posteriorly, could extend intracranially after maxillary sinus invasion (2). Patients with ameloblastoma may seek medical attention for signs and symptoms such as: a) a slow-growing swelling, b) facial asymmetry, c) loose teeth, d) pain, e) paresthesia, and so on, or the lesion may be discovered by chance on radiographs taken for routine dental examination (2, 5).

2. OBJECTIVE

The main objective of this article is to review the history, pathogenesis, classification with clinical and radiological features, and management of ameloblastoma.

3. METHODS

A literature review mainly of the Pubmed database was done using the keywords: “ameloblastoma pathogenesis”; “ameloblastoma classification”; “ameloblastoma history”; “clinical and radiological features of ameloblastoma”; and “management of ameloblastoma”.

4. RESULTS

Papers from the types of literature review, case series, case report, and research were selected and reviewed for ameloblastoma’s history, classification, pathogenesis, clinical and radiological features, and management.

5. DISCUSSION

History of Ameloblastoma

Ameloblastoma, is derived from the English word

“amel”, which means enamel, and the Greek word “blastos”, which means the germ. It was firstly described by Cusack in 1827, and named adamantinoma by the French physician Louis-Charles Malassez in 1885 and ameloblastoma by Ivey and Churchill in 1930 (6–8).

Pathogenesis of Ameloblastoma

Ameloblastoma derives from epithelial tissues associated with tooth formation, including the enamel organ, the epithelial cell rests of Malassez, the reduced enamel epithelium, and the lining of odontogenic cysts (9). Several theories have been put forward to explain the pathogenesis of ameloblastoma. Most of them suppose that the development and progression of the tumor could be related to the epithelial-mesenchymal transition (EMT) which is a complex process that enables dynamic changes in cells from an epithelial to a mesenchymal morphology. Studies suggest that EMT plays a pivotal role in mediating the migratory and invasive capabilities of many tumor cell types and leads to gene transcription changes (10, 11). Additionally, multiple factors, including gene mutations, are reported to be involved in the tumorigenesis and tumor progression of ameloblastoma, and mutations in several oncogenes, such as B-type Raf kinase (*BRAF*) and smoothed (*SMO*) (12–14).

Classification of Ameloblastoma

In 2017, ameloblastomas were classified by W.H.O into three categories: a) unicystic, b) conventional (formerly known as solid/multicystic), and c) extraosseous/peripheral (2, 15). It is important to note that in this new classification, the designation solid/multicystic was rejected to avoid possible confusion with the unicystic lesion, and the desmoplastic type, included in the old classifications, was reclassified as a histological subdivision (15, 16).

Unicystic Ameloblastoma

Unicystic ameloblastoma is a less aggressive subtype of intraosseous ameloblastomas with a low rate of recurrence. It represents 15% of all ameloblastomas and appears more frequently in the 2nd or 3rd decade. Clinically and radiologically, it resembles an odontogenic cyst (2).

Histopathologically, unicystic ameloblastomas present three subdivisions, based on the tumor cell proliferation extent inside the cyst wall: a) luminal, b) intraluminal, and c) mural (the lesion invades the wall acting as a conventional ameloblastoma) (15, 17).

Treatment of unicystic ameloblastomas remains controversial. For many surgeons, enucleation and curettage of the neighboring bone can be useful, especially in young patients and in luminal and intraluminal subtypes; for others, the high recurrence rates following conservative treatment protocols make radical surgical removal an indication (17, 18).

Conventional Ameloblastoma

Conventional ameloblastoma represents 86% of all ameloblastomas and occurs, usually, in the 3rd and 4th decades of life. It progresses slowly but invasively, infiltrating into contiguous tissue after eroding the cortical bone (2).

Radiographically, conventional ameloblastomas show extensive, radiolucent, multilocular images, with a typical “soap bubble-like” appearance. The cortical plate becomes thin, expanded, and sometimes eroded, with the linked non-erupted tooth displaced. The roots of the adjacent teeth undergo a clear resorption (19).

Histologically, several subtypes of conventional ameloblastoma can be identified based on cell morphological patterns: a) follicular, b) plexiform, c) acanthomatous, d) granular, e) desmoplastic, and f) basal. The follicular and plexiform subtypes present the highest incidence among the others (15, 20).

Due to an elevated recurrence rate (13–15%), radical surgery with 1.5–2 cm beyond the radiological margins and large resection of adjacent soft tissue is the treatment of choice for conventional ameloblastoma. A long-term follow-up is required (2, 20, 21).

Peripheral Ameloblastoma

Extraosseous/peripheral ameloblastoma is found exclusively in the gingival tissue and/or the alveolar mucosa (2); it infiltrates the adjacent tissues without involving the underlying bone.

Clinically, it presents as an exophytic lesion mimicking the fibrous epulis. Generally, no radiological evidence of bone involvement could be found. It mostly occurs in the premolar region of the mandible (32.6%), followed by the maxillary tuberosity (22).

Histologically, the peripheral type shows islands of ameloblastic epithelium with a pattern comparable to the conventional ameloblastoma (20).

Peripheral ameloblastomas are usually treated with a wide local excision (23, 24). However, considering the recurrence frequency reported (9% to 19%), a long-term follow-up is required (24).

Finally, it is important to highlight the presence of the metastasizing ameloblastomas; these entities present the same histological aspects as the non-metastasizing, and consequently the diagnosis can only be made when metastasis has taken place (25). Their etiology may include: a) large and/or recently diagnosed tumors; b) a high number of recurrences; c) failure of previous surgical treatments; and d) plexiform histology (26). Metastasizing ameloblastomas to the lung are the most frequent, followed by the cervical lymph nodes, the diaphragm, the liver, and the brain (25, 27).

For metastasizing ameloblastomas, radical surgery is indicated, followed by a mandatory, thorough long-term follow-up; the role of chemotherapy and/or radiation has yet to be defined (27).

It is to be noted that the following steps are mandatory to insure successful surgical treatment of ameloblastomas: a) the intermaxillary fixation aiming to retrieve the original occlusion; b) the preparation of the two landmarks intended to conserve the original position of the mandibular condyle in the glenoid fossa and the ramus; c) the placement of the reconstructive titanium plate designed to maintain the mandibular function and space; and d) the autogenous bone graft to replace the missing bone.

6. CONCLUSION

Ameloblastomas are usually identified at an advanced stage because of their late symptoms. Their management typically includes a large resection with safety margins and immediate reconstruction whenever possible. Regular long-term postoperative follow-ups are mandatory for optimum treatment outcome and recurrence prevention.

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